

Composition of Foreign Capital Inflows and Growth in India: An Empirical Analysis.

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Abstract

The role of foreign capital in economic growth has been a burning topic of debate in several countries including India. It is not possible for a developing country like India to grow without sufficient import of capital because of the gaps that exist in domestic savings and capital requirements. The Government of India has taken many initiatives to attract foreign capital to boost the Indian economy since liberalization. As a result, India has received Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) to the tune of US \$ 355415 million as at the end of December 2014. This study has assessed the growth of GDP and Exports along with the composition of foreign capital, i.e. Foreign Direct Investment, Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), External commercial Borrowings (ECBs), and NRI Deposits in India during the period 1991 to 2014 which is based on secondary data. This study has analyzed the trends of foreign capital inflows in the form of source wise, country wise and reveals that the effect of foreign capital inflows have a positive impact on GDP and Export except the source of ECBs on GDP, ECBs and NRI deposits on Export which both are not significant as per model formulation.

Keywords: *Gross Domestic Product, Foreign Direct Investment, Foreign Portfolio Investment, External Commercial Borrowings, NRI Deposits, Export*

Introduction

Foreign capital inflows have significant potential benefits for economies around the world. Countries with sound macroeconomic policies and well functioning institutions are in the best position to reap the benefits of capital flows and minimize the risks. During the initial stages of development, domestic savings are normally not adequate to finance the development projects required to achieve faster economic growth. Globally, a strong consensus has emerged that for achieving higher economic growth, a greater role of foreign investment is required. In 1991, Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization became part of Indian policy aimed at making the Indian economy a faster growing economy and globally competitive. Many forms of the foreign capital inflows have emerged since then, including ECBs, FDI, FPI and NRI Deposits. A series of reforms that have been undertaken with respect to Trade, Financial Sector (Banking & Insurance), Telecommunication, Real Estate, Construction Sector, etc. Such reforms have brought about a major boom and contributed to both employment and higher GDP growth of the Indian economy after liberalization. As a result, India has received FDI to the tune of US \$ 355415 million as at the end of December 2014. The FDI inflows have shown a rising trend from 1991-92 to 2013-14 owing to the sincere programmes of structural liberalization and open market reforms, except in the year 2008-09 which shows a negative trend due to the global crisis. But again, in the following years, foreign investment started to bounce back.

Composition of Foreign Capital

India is a developing country, and like many other developing countries, international capital inflows had significantly benefited the Indian economy. International capital flow, such as FDI and FPI flows, has been a huge contribution to positively influence the economic behavior and growth trajectory of the developing countries. There are many forms of the foreign capital inflows, including Commercial Borrowings, FDI, FPI and NRI deposits. Table 1 shows the composition of foreign capital inflows in India over the period of liberalization to the current scenario. The composition of capital inflows has changed significantly over the years. Among these, there has been a gradual shift away from debt components to equity flows. During the year 2007-08, percentage contribution of ECBs is the highest among all the modes of inflows.

The representation of trends in foreign capital inflow is as per Figure 1. Figure one reveals that after the liberalization, flow of foreign capital has been a consistent till the year 2002-03, but after that there has been much fluctuation in the flow of foreign capital into India. The downward mark in the above Figure 1 represents a huge drop in the trend of foreign capital inflows during the recession in year 2008-09. The composition of foreign capital inflows is presented in Table 1 and reveals that in the decade up to 2000, the percentage of debt has grown more as compared to equity, but in the second decade, i.e. after 2000, the percentage of equity has grown more as compared to debt which is a positive sign for the Indian economy.

Table 1: Foreign Capital Inflows in terms of US \$ million

Year	FDI	FPI	NRI	ECBs
1990-91	97	6	1536	2248
1991-92	129	4	290	1456
1992-93	315	244	2001	-358
1993-94	586	3567	1207	608
1994-95	1314	3824	172	1030
1995-96	2144	2748	1104	1275
1996-97	2821	3313	3350	2848
1997-98	3557	1828	1125	3999
1998-99	2462	-61	961	4362
1999-00	2155	3026	1540	313
2000-01	3272	2590	2316	4308
2001-02	4734	1952	2754	-1588
2002-03	3217	944	2978	-1701
2003-04	2388	11356	3642	-2928
2004-05	3713	9287	-964	5426
2005-06	3034	12494	2789	2759
2006-07	7693	7060	4321	16443
2007-08	15893	27433	179	22641
2008-09	22372	-14030	4290	6647
2009-10	17966	32396	2922	2531
2010-11	11834	30293	3238	11832
2011-12	22061	17170	11918	9140
2012-13	19819	26891	14842	8582
2013-14	21564	4822	38892	10716

The country-wise FDI inflow into India from the top five investing countries is presented in Table 2. The major investing countries in India are Mauritius, USA, Singapore, UK, Netherlands, Japan, Germany and others. The table reveals that Mauritius has been investing the most in various sectors of the Indian economy and is among the top 5 investing countries in India from Jan. 2000 to Dec. 2014. Out of total FDI inflows from the top 5 countries, 35% is from Mauritius as the most dominant source contributing US \$ 84417 million. It is because that India has a Double Taxation Avoidance Agreement (DTAA) with Mauritius. This type of taxation has been made out with Singapore

Table 2: Top Five Investing Countries FDI Equity Inflows (US\$ in million)

Country	2012-13 (Ap-Mar)	2013-14 (Ap-Mar)	2014-15 (Ap-Dec14)	Cumulative inflow (Ap 00-Dec14)	% in total inflow
Mauritius	9497	4859	5892	84417	35%
Singapore	2308	5985	4313	29758	13%
U.K.	1080	3215	1029	21793	9%
Japan	2237	1718	1427	17695	7%
Nether Land	1856	2270	2579	13815	6%

(Source: DIPP, FDI Statistics)

So Singapore is the second largest investor of FDI inflow in India i.e. US \$ 29758 million. But the amount of inflow has decreased in the year 2014 as compared to year 2012 in the case of Mauritius whereas Singapore has shown an increase during this period. The other major countries are U.K with a relative share US \$ 21793 million, followed by Japan and Netherland. While some countries like Cyprus, Germany, France and Switzerland have a lower share in FDI inflow of the top ten countries.

Review of Literature

The relationship between economic growth and foreign investment has been a subject of discussion for many years. Khanna (2002) examines the macroeconomic impact on the Indian capital market as well as the corporate sector, the macroeconomic effects due inflow of capital, and also the micro-economic effects on the capital market between 1989 and 2002. He considered Foreign Direct Investment, Portfolio Investment and external assistance and GDP/GDS/GNP as variables for the study. He finds that the entry of international capital flows helped to provide greater depth to the domestic capital market and reduce the systematic risk of the economy. He argues that liberalizing the capital market and opening them to foreign investment has increased the availability of capital with domestic industries and commercial firms. On the other hand, the Indian stock market today is dominated by a small group of FIIs. He concludes that in the case of India, the microanalysis of stock markets has also failed to provide any evidence that the entry of FII has reduced the cost of the Indian corporate sector.

Kohli (2003), examines how capital flows affect a range of economic variables such as interest rates of foreign exchange reserves, exchange rates, domestic monetary condition and financial system in India during the period 1986 to 2001. She examines how capital inflows induce a real exchange rate appreciation, stock market and real estate boom, real accumulation and monetary expansion as well as effects on production and consumption. Inflows of foreign capital have a significant impact on domestic money supply and stock market growth, liquidity and volatility.

Rachidi and Saidi (2011) find that FDI has a significant positive impact on real per capita growth. Also, no evidence was found that Portfolio Investment enhances output growth in developing countries. In a random effect, the coefficient of FDI remains positive but statistically insignificant, and portfolio investment remains negative and insignificant for all the countries. However, this is positive and significant for developed countries, when the GMM estimator is used.

Chipalkatti and Rishi (2001) estimate that Indian capital flight in 1997 was at US \$ 88 billion and during the period 1971 to 97, a sum of 20 percent of the US \$ 448 billion external debt disbursed to the country over the same time period and generated a strong evidence of year wise correlation between debt inflows and flight-capital outflows.

Malik (2010) explored the relationship of external debt and economic growth in Pakistan for the period of 1972 to 2005. A simple OLS model was used for analysis, the results showed a negative and significant relation between external debt and economic growth. The same stands good for the relation between debt servicing and economic growth.

Sharma (2000) used a multiple regression to evaluate the role of FDI on the export performance in the Indian economy. The study concluded that FDI does not have a statistically significant role in the export promotion in Indian economy. This result is also confirmed by the study of Pailwar (2001) who argues that the foreign firms are more interested in the large Indian market rather than aiming for the global market.

So, we observe that several studies have analyzed only the relationship of FDI as a foreign inflow variable to various macro economic variables rather than other sources of foreign capital in India like FPI, ECBs and NRI deposits. Therefore, we formulate a model where GDP and Export depends on the FDI, FPI, ECBs and NRI deposits along with Export and Import. Details of the methodological framework have been described in the next section.

Objective and Research Methodology

Foreign capital is composed of FDI, FPI, ECBs NRI deposits which as mentioned below in the model formulation are the variable which have an effect on the growth of Indian GDP and Export, the main objective of this paper. So as per objective, formulation of the hypothesis is

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between Foreign inflow variables and Gross Domestic Product of India.

H1₁: There is a significant relationship between Foreign inflow variables and Gross Domestic Product of India.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between Foreign inflow variables and Export of India.

H1₂: There is a significant relationship between Foreign inflow variables and Export of India.

Model Formulation

$$\text{GDP} = f(\text{FDI, FPI, ECB, NRI, EXPORT, IMPORT}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{EXPORT} = f(\text{FDI, FPI, ECB, NRI, GDP, IMPORT}) \quad (2)$$

Where as

GDP Gross domestic product

FDI Foreign direct investment

FPI Foreign portfolio investment

ECB External commercial borrowings

NRI Non resident of Indian Deposits

Data Collection and Research Methodology

The data set of foreign capital inflow consists of different variables including FDI, FPI, ECB and NRI which are a function of GDP and Export. The data set is secondary and covers the time period after the liberalization of Indian economy to the current scenario and the data was collected from the Department of industrial policy and promotion, Economic Surveys, annual publications of Reserve Bank of India and various journals.

Regression and correlation analysis is one of the most commonly used statistical techniques used in almost all fields. Its main objective is to explore the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (which are also called predictor or explanatory variables).

We used the technique of correlation to test the statistical significance of the association between FDI, FPI, ECB, NRI and GDP of Indian economy. Correlation helps to measure the strength and direction of a linear association between variables.

Analysis

Table-3 presents the descriptive statistics of the selected variables. Note that variables have been considered in terms of US \$ million and foreign inflow variables as per balance of payment. It has been observed that during the period 1991-2014 India's average GDP at market price measured US \$ 805149 million.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Selected Variables

	FDI	FPI	ECB	NRI	GDP	EXPORT	IMPORT
Mean	7297.50	7881.54	4691.20	4475.12	805149.90	103687.1	152417.50
Median	3244.50	3440.00	2803.50	2535.00	507694.50	48639.50	56412.50
Maximum	22372.00	32396.00	22641.00	38892.00	1880154.00	312621.0	490737.00
Minimum	97.00	-14030.00	-2928.00	-964.00	252807.00	17865.00	19411.00
Std. Dev.	7944.82	11340.41	6045.49	8127.04	564487.60	100390.4	161048.80
Skewness	0.96	0.83	1.35	3.44	0.90	1.06	1.06
Kurtosis	2.26	3.15	4.613	14.77	2.32	2.69	2.66
Jarque-Bera	4.28	2.81	9.96	186.06	3.69	4.61	4.61
Probability	0.11	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.09	0.09

Source: Authors' computation based on secondary source of data

The average inflow of FDI during this period was US \$ 7297.50 million. The description of overall foreign inflows shows that during the period under consideration average foreign inflows was US \$ 24344 million, which was 3 percent of average GDP over this period. The average value of Import of India is closely 1.5 times of average export value over the liberalization period.

In any time series analysis we need to check the stationarity of the series. Table 4 depicts results of augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF), Dickey Fuller test and Phillips Perron (PP) test for unit root in connection with the variables. ADF statistics for all the variables, except NRI, are statistically significant at first difference whereas FPI is stationary at level. The test statistics of PP test, which are more appropriate shows statistically significant for all the variables under consideration. It confirms that the variables have no unit root when a year lag is considered to check the dependency of GDP. These findings rationalize our objective to find the impact of foreign inflow variables and other macroeconomic variables on economic growth. Therefore, all the variables under consideration are stationary.

Table 4: Unit root test for Selected Variables

Variables	ADF	DF	PP
GDP	-3.3557*	-4.1468*	-3.5201***
FDI	-4.8209*	-4.9362*	-5.2716*
FPI	-6.5317*	-9.6055*	-4.2113*
ECB	-4.8189*	-5.0731*	-10.8601*
NRI	1.5991	-0.9518	-7.2011*
EXPORT	-6.1110*	-5.6067*	-3.5616**
IMPORT	-6.4701*	-1.1239	-2.6988***
GFCF	-4.1247*	-3.7709*	-4.1247*
INF	-6.6590*	-5.3013*	-6.9133*
COMPEMP	-4.5920*	-4.6876*	-4.7967*

* significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5% level, *** significant at 10% level

Source: Authors' computation based on secondary source of data

The results of the regression analysis have been depicted in table 5. Number of models have been analyzed in between the variables to check the impact of foreign inflow variables on GDP and Export. The value of R^2 and Durbin-Watson statistics confirm that our model specification is statistically significant. The test statistics of the FDI, FPI and NRI in model 1 where GDP is dependent variable, shows that, except the ECB all the variables have positive impact on GDP and statistically significant at 1% level of significance, whereas in model 2, NRI and IMPORT have negative impact on GDP and statistically significant at 1% level. In both models 1 and 2, ECB is not significant and it indicates that FDI, FPI and EXPORT speeds up the economic growth of India.

As per model second where EXPORT is dependent variable, model 1 depicts that only FDI and FPI have positive impact on EXPORT and statistically significant at 1% level. Whereas in model 2 and 3, only GDP has positive impact on the EXPORT and statistically significant but IMPORT has negative impact on the flow of EXPORT and statistically significant at 5% level.

Table 5: Estimated Results of the Model

Dependent Variable GDP			Dependent Variable EXPORT			
Coefficients Model			Coefficients Model			
Variables	1	2	Variables	1	2	3
FDI	7.348*	3.143*	FDI	3.354*	-0.627	-0.125
FPI	7.348*	4.066*	FPI	3.082*	0.156	-0.524
ECB	0.871	-0.260	ECB	1.090	0.679	0.301
NRI	3.232*	-2.840*	NRI	0.995	-0.902	-1.052
EXPORT	-	6.898*	GDP	-	3.139*	3.612*
IMPORT	-	-2.911*	IMPORT	-	-	-2.354**
R^2	0.946	0.997	R^2	0.820	0.884	0.912
A. R^2	0.935	0.996	A. R^2	0.782	0.851	0.881
D.W	2.097	1.023	D.W	0.656	0.404	0.698
Prob (F-stat)	0.000	0.000	Prob (F-stat)	0.000	0.000	0.000

* significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5% level, *** significant at 10% level, figures represent t-values

Source: Authors computation based on secondary

source of data

Finally, we observe that FDI and FPI have positive impact on GDP and it is statistically significant whereas the result of ECB is insignificant. It means that part of equity investment boost up the growth of Indian economy as compare to external debt. The flow of equity has grown more as compared to debt after the year 2000 which is a positive sign for the growth of Indian economy. On the other hand, FDI, FPI and GDP have positive impact on the growth of EXPORT and statistically significant but again the results of ECB and NRI are insignificant.

Conclusion

We cannot imagine faster economic growth without knowing the trends and behavior of foreign capital flows into India. Various forms of foreign capital inflows have been generated after the period of liberalization. FDI as a strategic component of investment is needed by India for its sustained economic growth, which boosts the economy the most as compared to other sources as per analysis. The flow of equity has grown more as compared to debt after the year 2000 which is a positive sign for the growth of Indian economy. Mauritius is the most dominating mode of foreign equity inflow in India among all the countries, i.e., 36 percent of the total equity inflow. It is because that India has a Double Taxation Avoidance Agreement (DTAA) with Mauritius. Singapore is the second dominant, which has increased its contribution up to 16 percent from 2000 to 2014. The current study shows a positive and significant impact of foreign capital inflows on GDP and Export, except the effect of ECBs on the GDP, FPI and ECBs on Export since liberalization. In future work, a computational model will be designed at sectoral level to enhance the accuracy of our model using other macroeconomic variables.

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